

FAIR Data and Software Management in the Process Industry

A Cross-Consortia Use Case from Engineering Science, Process and Chemical Development on Data Management in Highly Regulated Industries

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Abstract

In highly regulated sectors such as the process industry, the lack of standardized, well-documented data poses a significant barrier to transparency, reproducibility, and regulatory approval. This work showcases how combining contributions from **five NFDI consortia** - **NFDI4Cat**, **NFDI4Chem**, **NFDI4ING**, **DAPHNE4NFDI**, and **NFDI4CS** - can unlock added value and support regulatory readiness, and illustrates how interoperable building blocks can support a FAIR, future-ready data ecosystem for industrial applications in the process industry, as is shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1: From lab development to modular production supported by NFDI. Image: ©Sascha Lamm & Peter Pelz

NFDI4Cat and **NFDI4ING** promote data interoperability and reuse in modular process plants through cooperative initiatives like the **ENPRO-REUNION** project, where TU Darmstadt and Industrial Science developed the Semantic PEA Data sheet (**SPEAD**) - a semantic graph-based documentation format for Process Equipment Assemblies (**PEAs**) integrated into the Asset Administration Shell (**AAS**) [1]. **SPEAD** captures technical and process-relevant data in a machine-readable, standardized format, enabling digitalized plant documentation and fostering synergies with other modularization efforts.

NFDI4ING promotes **SPEAD** development by providing tools for handling heterogeneous data and creating FAIR metadata templates. **NFDI4ING** also introduced Sensor Interfacing Language (**SOIL**), a domain-specific meta-model that captures sensor data semantics and communication. At TU Dortmund, a collaboration between **ENPRO** and **NFDI4Cat** is developing a core metadata model that complements **SPEAD** by linking core-engineering data to research from catalysis science. This includes reusing **metadata4ing** and domain terminology such as STRENDA biocatalysis guidelines, and contributes to joint efforts with **NFDI4Chem** on a central metadata model for improved data discoverability.

For the preceding lab development, **NFDI4Chem** offers smart lab solutions for fully digital workflows. The open-source Electronic Lab Notebook (**ELN**) Chemotion [2], which is already used successfully in the chemical industry, allows automated data acquisition, analysis and management. Further, the LabImotion extension [3] adds customized functionalities, enabling the implementation of workflows from catalysis - together with **NFDI4Cat** and **CRC1441 TrackAct** - and research at large data facilities - together with **DAPHNE4NFDI** and **ROCK-IT**.

In the context of large-scale facilities, **DAPHNE4NFDI** evaluates [4] and integrates automation systems [5], sensors, digital twins and comprehensive datasets into a coherent workflow, and also exerts formative influence on the development of products like BlueSky Automation, SciCat, and Labmotion. Concurrently, it advances its own suite of analytical tools, such as **AIXtal** Refinement Platform for First-Time Users [6] and **SNIP**, a collaborative ELN that unifies digital excerpts with handwritten annotations, schematic illustrations, and FAIR-compliant metadata capture [4], thereby establishing fully interoperable, reproducible and reusable digital research at large scale infrastructures.

In the future, the Research Data Management Container (**RDMC**) by **NFDixCS** could offer another useful toolbox to package all necessary artifacts from various domains, such as software, data, and their context through a predefined workflow [7]. This could further be enhanced by emerging common metadata standards of **One NFDI**. RDMCs act as time capsules, ensuring that all artifacts remain unchangeable. An initially constructed Reusable Execution Environment (**REE**) can be used to unpack the artifacts and rerun the experiment in a predefined environment.

Keywords: Interoperability, Semantic Modeling, Structured Documentation, Metadata, Research Data and Software Management

Resources

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Competing interests

The authors declare that they have no competing interests.

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